

Artificial Intelligence for Academic Libraries

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Abstract

The aim of the present paper is how Artificial Intelligence (AI) is boon for academic libraries. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is one of the emerging technology of this era. AI has been associated with several trades like defense, health, business and education. But it's role in academic library services will faster intelligent decisions It is widely used technology in academic library services that can transform the best services in the age of information technology. Present paper aims to highlights the use of AI in library operations. Let's see how Artificial Intelligence (AI) is important for academic libraries.

Keywords

Artificial Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence in academic libraries, Advantages of Artificial Intelligence, Challenges of Artificial Intelligence.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence is the technology that enables machines to have the abilities to plan, learn, reason, solve problems, move and to some extent be creative. AI can offer several benefits to libraries and librarians and their users, such as improving the efficiency and accuracy of library data, increasing the relevance and diversity of resources and services, expanding access to information and supporting innovation and learning. It also reduce manual and repetitive tasks for library staff. AI can be applied to various aspects of library services like classification, reference service, acquisition, cataloging, preservation and indexing. For example AI can help librarians provide personalized and relevant recommendations to their users, based on their preference, behaviour and context.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is one of the emerging trends and applications of computing in libraries. It involves programming computers to do things, which if done by humans, would be said to require intelligence. Artificial intelligence will greatly improve library operations and services and will upgrade the heighten the relevance of libraries in an ever-changing digital society. With the help of the artificial intelligence we can save time, money and efforts. In this way artificial intelligence is very important technology for academic libraries in this digital era.

Artificial Intelligence In Academic Libraries

AI can be used in various fields of library services these are as follows.

1. Automatic indexing using expert system.
2. Automatic classification using optical character reorganization.
3. Automatic cataloging using optical character reorganization.
4. Automatic acquisition system.
5. In reference services.
6. In different library activities.

Artificial Intelligence already touches many of our daily computing activities. AI is used in many areas such as business, military, education, libraries etc. Unless libraries begin to exploit the new technologies and innovate their information services delivery, they may face obsolescence in this generation.

Advantages of Artificial Intelligence In Academic Libraries

There are many advantages of AI in academic libraries. It can be summarized as follows.

1. Finished task quicker than a human.
2. To minimization of efforts.
3. Maximization of efficiency.
4. To immersive user experience.
5. To save space.
6. To improve libraries status. 7.Success ratio is great.
8. To save money.
9. Multiple functions can do a time.

Challenges Of Implementing Artificial Intelligence In Academic Libraries

There are some limitations to implementing AI system in academic libraries. AI systems are generally not in operational use in most libraries.

1. Lack of funds.
2. Lack of trend manpower.
3. Lack of space.
4. Lack of power supply.
5. Lack of internet connectivity.
6. Lack of proper guidance.
7. Lack of infrastructure.

So in this way there are many obstacles in implementing AI system in academic libraries.

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence has gained tremendous application in library information services like user structured information environment, smart Document Delivery Services, Intelligent gateways to online sources etc. AI can help librarians discover new and emerging topics. To improve library and librarians status AI is very useful technology. To improve classification of library resources, to improve circulation services, to improve reference services AI is very useful. One of the major benefit of AI is that it's conclusion is based on data rather than emotions. Even after our best efforts it is known fact that human decisions are always biased in a negative way by our emotions. So in this way AI is very very important technology for library and librarians in today's fastest age.

References

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